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FILOLOGIYA

1. Ахмедов Ойбек Сапорбаевич ИҚТИСОДИЁТГА ОИД ЛЕКСИК БИРЛИКЛАРНИНГ ТАРЖИМА ҚИЛИШ МУАММОЛАРИ.....	14
2. Краева Вероника Юриевна СВАДЕБНЫЙ ОБРЯД РУССКИХ НА ТЕРРИТОРИИ ВТОРИЧНОГО ЗАСЕЛЕНИЯ АЛТАЯ.....	21
3. Saparova Mohira Fayzullayevna THE DEVELOPMENT ISSUES OF PRIVATE HIGHER EDUCATION IN NEW UZBEKISTAN.....	28
4. Masharipova Yulduz Otaxanovna LINGUOCULTUROLOGICAL STUDY OF THE NOVEL “O‘TKAN KUNLAR” AND ITS’ TRANSLATION VERSIONS INTO THE ENGLISH LANGUAGE.....	34
5. Куляпин Александр Иванович РЕАЛЬНОСТЬ И МИФ В ПОВЕСТИ ВАЛЕРИЯ ПОПОВА «КОМАР ЖИВЕТ, ПОКА ПОЕТ».....	47
6. Якубов Музаффар Камилджанович XVI АСР ИНГЛИЗ УЙҒОНИШ ДАВРИ ДРАМАТУРГИЯСИДА АМИР ТЕМУР ШАХСИ ТАЛҚИНИ.....	54
7. Махмудов Умиджан Реимбаевич НОРМАТИВНЫЕ ДАННЫЕ ПЕРЦЕПТИВНЫХ КОМПОНЕНТОВ СЕМАНТИКИ СЛОВ УЗБЕКСКОГО ЯЗЫКА.....	64
8. Аблаева Надира Кадамжановна «ТЕНЬ МОЯ НА СТЕНАХ ТВОИХ». (Восточные мотивы в творчестве Анны Ахматовой).	74
9. Марьяна Ольга Викторовна СИНТЕЗ СИНТАКСИЧЕСКИХ СРЕДСТВ СВЯЗИ КАК ПОКАЗАТЕЛЬ ТЕКСТОВОЙ ИНТЕГРАЦИИ (НА МАТЕРИАЛЕ ХУДОЖЕСТВЕННЫХ ПРОИЗВЕДЕНИЙ РУБЕЖА XX-XXI).....	80
10. Xudaybergenova Umida Komildjanovna ERGONIMLARNING O‘RGANILISHI MASALASIGA DOIR MULOHAZALAR.....	85
11. Исмаилова Феруза Исмаиловна ПОСЛОВИЦЫ О ПОСЛОВИЦАХ. ВЗГЛЯДЫ ПИСАТЕЛЕЙ НА ПОСЛОВИЦЫ.....	91
12. Джуманиязова Интизор Давлатназар кизи МЕТОДИКА ПРЕПОДАВАНИЯ РУССКОГО ЯЗЫКА В НАЦИОНАЛЬНЫХ ГРУППАХ И ОСОБЕННОСТИ ИЗУЧЕНИЯ ЛЕКСИЧЕСКОГО МИНИМУМА.....	97
13. Каримов Хикматбек Анварович ГРАММАТИЧЕСКИЕ ОСОБЕННОСТИ ПОСТРОЕНИЯ ФРАЗЕОЛОГИЧЕСКИХ ЕДИНИЦ.....	104

14. Raximbayeva Yulduz Sattar qizi, Tojiyev Jahongir Ko‘pal o‘g‘li “DEVONU LUG‘ATIT TURK” ASARIDA RANG IFODALOVCHI LEKSEMALAR.....	109
--	-----

FALSAFA

15. Нарзулла Жўраев СИЁСАТ ИЖТИМОЙИ ҲОДИСА СИФАТИДА.....	115
--	-----

16. Yegane Bakhshiyeva, Ferahile Babayeva-Shukurova ARMENIA-AZERBAIJAN CONFLICT: HISTORY AND REALITIES.....	121
---	-----

17. Мадрахим Сафарбоев, Отабек Сафарбоев АЛИШЕР НАВОЙИ АСАРЛАРИДА НАЖМИДДИН КУБРО ВАСФИ.....	133
--	-----

18. Sharof Agabayev YOSHLAR SIYOSIY TOLERANTLIGI GLOBALLASHUV JARAYONINING MURAKKAB FENOMENI SIFATIDA.....	139
--	-----

19. Саидназаров Улуғбек Ахмеджанович, Рузметов Шерзод Арслон ўғли ЖИСМОНИЙ МАДАНИЯТ – МУАЙЯН ТАРИХИЙ ШАРОИТ МАҲСУЛИ СИФАТИДА.....	144
--	-----

20. Rasulov Rustambek YANGI O‘ZBEKISTONDA YOSHLAR BILAN ISHLASH TIZIMIDA ULARNING IJTIMOIIY FAOLLIGI VA MA’NAVIY SALOHIIYATINI RIVOJLANTIRISHNING O‘ZIGA XOS MECHANIZMLARI.....	151
---	-----

PEDAGOGIKA VA PSIXOLOGIYA

21. Уразбаева Дилбар Абдуллаевна ОНКОЛОГИК БЕМОРЛАР ИЖТИМОЙИ-ПСИХОЛОГИК ҲОЛАТИНИ ТАДҚИҚ ҚИЛИШ ХУСУСИЯТЛАРИ.....	157
--	-----

22. Nyutonova Xilola Lochinbekovna MAHMUDXO‘JA BEMBUDIY “PADARKUSH” ASARINING PEDAGOGIK TAHLILI.....	164
--	-----

23. Sharifzoda Sardorbek GENDER PEDAGOGIKASINING DOLZARB MUAMMOLARI.....	171
--	-----

24. Xudoyberganova Maqsuda Jumaniyazovna OLIY TA‘LIMDA KAFEDRA TIZIMIDAGI HAMKORLIKNI EMPIRIK JIHATDAN O‘RGANISH.....	177
---	-----

25. Allaberganova Go‘zal Adilbek qizi ONKOLOGIK BEMORLAR KOGNITIV JARAYONLARINI O‘RGANISH.....	187
--	-----

26. Jumaboyeva Mahliyo Xudaybergan qizi TALABALARDA IRODAVIY XUSUSIYATLARNI SHAKLLANTIRISHNING PSIXOLOGIK SHART-SHAROITLARI.....	193
--	-----

27. Qurbonova Shaxloxon Baxadirovna
BEMOR PSIXOLOGIYASIGA DOIR AGRESSIV HOLATLARNING O'RGANILISHI.....199

TIBBIYOT

28. Абдуллаев Равшанбек Бабажонович, Махмудова Лола Иззатуллоевна
ОРОЛ БЎЙИ ҲУДУДИДА ЯРА КАСАЛЛИГИНИ ДАВОЛАШГА ЯНГИЧА
ЁНДАШИШ.....205

29. Розиходжаева Гулнора Ахмедовна, Шарипова Зухрожон Камиловна
АЁЛЛАРДА ЮРАК-ҚОН ТОМИР ХАВФИНИ СТРАТИФИКАЦИЯСИДА СУТ БЕЗИ
АРТЕРИЯСИ КАЛЬЦИФИКАЦИЯСИНИНГ АҲАМИЯТИ.....210

TARIX

30. Аширов Адҳамжон Азимбаевич
СУВ БИЛАН БОҒЛИҚ МИФОЛОГИК ҚАРАШЛАР.....218

31. Вахид Омаров
ДЕЯТЕЛЬНОСТЬ АРМЯНСКОЙ ПАРТИИ ДАШНАКЦУТЮН В ГРУЗИНСКОЙ ССР.....225

32. Umid Bekmuhammad
ANNA GERMAN AND KHOREZM.....233

33. Кулаков Владимир Олегович
РЕАЛИЗАЦИЯ ТОРГОВОЙ ПОЛИТИКИ РОССИИ С ПЕРСИЕЙ ЧЕРЕЗ
АСТРАХАНЬ В XVIII ВЕКЕ.....251

34. Ferhat ÇİFTÇİ
НАУВЕР GEÇİDİ'NİN TARİHİ COĞRAFYASI ÜZERİNE BAZI NOTLAR.....257

35. Zamonov Zokir Turg'inovich
TARAQQIYOTNING YANGI BOSQICHIDA O'ZBEKISTONDA MA'NAVIY ASOSLARNI
RIVOJLANTIRISHNING MEYORIY ASOSLARI (qisqacha tarixiy tahlilda).....269

36. Matkarimova Sadokat Maksudovna, Matkarimova Nazokat Maksudovna
XORAZM VOHASI BAXSHICHILIK SAN'ATI TARIXIDAN (Go'ro'g'li turkum
dostonlarining ilmiy tadqiqotlarda o'rganilishi).....277

37. Скубневский Валерий Анатольевич, Гончаров Юрий Михайлович
ГОРОДА СИБИРИ ВТОРОЙ ПОЛОВИНЫ XIX – НАЧАЛА XX В.....283

38. Озодбек Раджабов
МАРКАЗИЙ ОСИЁДА ЭЛЧИЛИК МУНОСАБАТЛАРИНИНГ ТАРИХИЙ ГЕНЕЗИСИ...295

39. Tahir Şahbazov
“KÜLTÜREL DEVRİM” DÖNEMİNDE (XX. YÜZYILIN 20-30'LU YILLARI)
AZERBAIJAN'DA KÜLTÜREL ORTAM.....304

40. Tadjiyeva Feruza Jumabayevna
ZAMAXSARIY FAOLIYATI VA U YASHAGAN DAVRNING IJTIMOYIY-SIYOSIY VA
MADANIY MUHITI.....316

41. Turaboyeva Zilola SURXON VOHASI MODDIY MADANIY MEROSI MILODDAN AVVALGI X – V ASRLARGA TEGISHLI KUCHUKTEPA ARXEOLOGIK OB’EKTINING BUGUNGI KUNDAGI MUHOFAZA HOLATINI O’RGANISH.....	322
42. Salayev Dilshod Jumanazarovich, Bekchanov Doniyor Baxramovich JADIDLAR MARKAZIY OSIYODA ZAMONAVIY TA’LIMNING ASOSCHILARI: XORAZM JADIDLARI MISOLIDA.....	330
43. Чуркин Михаил Константинович СИБИРЬ В ИМПЕРСКОЙ ГЕОГРАФИИ ВЛАСТИ: ПАТТЕРНЫ ОБЩЕСТВЕННО- ПОЛИТИЧЕСКОГО ДИСКУРСА XVI – XX ВВ.....	337
44. Matkarimov Xamidbek Olimbaevich, Sultonov Samandar Maxmud ўғли БРОНЗА ДАВРИ ХОРАЗМ ВОҲАСИ МАДАНИЯТЛАРИНИНГ (ТОЗАБОҒЁБ ВА АМИРОБОД) ПАЙДО БЎЛИШИ ВА РИВОЖЛАНИШИ.....	347
45. Абдалов Умидбек Матниязович ХОРАЗМ ВОҲАСИ ЎЗБЕКЛАРИ ТУРМУШИДА МОТАМ: АНЪАНАВИЙЛИК ВА ТРАНСФОРМАЦИЯ МАСАЛАЛАРИ.....	353
46. Karimov Sarvarbek Otabayevich, Matniyozov Sarvarbek Sanatbek o’g’li QADIMGI XORAZM HARBIY ISTEHKOMLARINING ASOSIY ELEMENTLARI.....	362
47. Karimov Umrbek Davronbekovch МАХМУД ҚОШГ‘АРИЙНИНГ “DEVONU LUG‘ATIT TURK”ДА ТУРКИЙ ХАЛҚЛАР КИЙИМ-БОШЛАРИ БАЙОНИ.....	369
48. Ismoilov Shohruxmirzo Zokirjon o’g’li МА’МУНИЙЛАР СУЛОЛАСИНИНГ ҲОКИМИЯТГА КЕЛИШИ ВА ЕТНОГЕНЕЗ МАСАЛАСИ.....	376
49. Raxmanova Shirin Qutlimuratovna KASHTACHILIKDA RANG TANLASH VA CHOKLARNING QO‘LLANILISHI TARIXI VA AHAMIYATI.....	383
50. Rozmetova Roziyajon Baxram qizi XORAZM VOHASI AN’ANAVIY UY-JOYLARI VA ULARNING LOKAL XUSUSIYATLARI.....	389
IQTISODIYOT	
51. Xo’janiyozov Nuriddin Yo’ldoshevich QIMMATLI QOG‘OZLAR BOZORINI RAQAMLI TEXNOLOGIYALAR ORQALI RIVOJLANTIRISH YO‘LLARI.....	395
52. Mavlanova Barchinoy TURIZMDA RAQAMLI MARKETING XIZMATLARI.....	403

SHARQ GAVHARI XIVA SHAHRIDA MA'MUN UNIVERSITETI NODAVLAT TA'LIM MUASSASASINING FAOLIYATI

O'zbekiston hududida sivilizatsiya va davlatchilikning shakllanishida qadimiy madaniyat o'choqlaridan biri Xorazm muhim o'rin tutgan. Binobarin "O'zbek davlatchiligining tamal toshlari bundan 2700 yil muqaddam ayni Xorazm vohasida qo'yilgan. Shu ma'noda, milliy davlatchiligimiz tarixi Misr, Xitoy, Hindiston, Yunoniston, Eron kabi eng qadimiy davlatlar bilan bir qatorda turadi. Xorazm tarixi o'zbek davlatchiligiga oid ulkan ma'lumotlar, moddiy va yozma yodgorliklar to'plangan tarixni asosi, uning qudrati va qadimiyligining tasdig'idir".

Davlatchilikka asos solinishi uchun, avvalombor, huquqiy asos bo'lishi kerak va shu ma'noda Xorazmda huquq ilmi ham shu davrlarda shakllangan. Shuningdek, Xorazm zaminidan yetishib chiqqan ilm-u fan namoyondalari yaratgan asarlar jahon tamadduni xazinasiga qo'shilgan katta hissa ekanligi barchamizga ma'lum.

Bu borada ayniqsa, XI asr boshida tashkil etilgan Xorazm Ma'mun akademiyasi (Majlisi ulamo) allomalarining qomusiy ilmiy faoliyati jahon ilm-fani taraqqiyotini yangi pog'onaga ko'taradi, bu faoliyat rakursini kengaytirib yubordi. Xorazm Ma'mun akademiyasi jahon ilmiy tafakkur tadriji, madaniy va ma'naviy taraqqiyotining benazr durdonasi sifatida tarixda chuqur, o'chmas iz qoldirgan.

Dunyo sivilizatsiyasi tarixida bunday markazlar o'zining mustahkam asoslariga, qadimiy ildizlarga egadir. Jumladan, insoniyat tarixidagi ilk akademiya, Aflotun akademiyasining "Bog' suhbatlari" – olimlarining turli mavzular bo'yicha bahs-munozalar shaklida voqelangan bo'lsa, keyingi davrlardagi ilmiy markazlar olimlarning doimiy ilmiy faoliyati bilan shug'ullanuvchi uyushmalariga aylangan. Ushbu an'analar islom davrida yangi bosqichga ko'tarilgan. IX asrda Bag'dodda tashkil topgan ikkinchi akademiya – "Bayt ul-hikma" Sharqning to'ng'ich akademiyalaridan sanalib, mazkur ilmiy dargohda ijod qilgan olimlarning aksari, jumladan, Muhammad al-Xorazmiy, Ahmad al-Farg'oniy, Ahmad al-Marvaziy, Abbos al-Javhariy va boshqalar Movarounnahr zaminidan yetishib chiqqan taniqli allomalar va mutafakkirlar edi. Ular tomondan yaratilgan bebaho asarlar va ilmiy kashfiyotlar keyinchalik Xorazm Ma'mun akademiyasi olimlar jamoasining nazariy va amaliy ilmlar sohasida erishgan yutuqlari uchun ma'naviy asos bo'lgan edi.

Tadqiqotlarga ko'ra, O'rta Osiyoda IX asrgacha shahar madaniyati beto'xtov rivojlanib, IX-XII asrlar ushbu o'lka xalqlari uchun buyuk yuksalish davri bo'lgan. Xorazm hukmdorlarining faol harakati tufayli XI asrning ikkinchi yarmida Ma'muniy xorazmshohlar davlati vujudga kelib, mamlakatning siyosiy, iqtisodiy va madaniy jihatdan yuksalishi davri bo'ldi. Ayniqsa, Ma'mun ibn Muhammad (992-997), Ali ibn Ma'mun (997-1009) davrida Xorazmda davlat mustaqilligi mustahkamlanib, uning harbiy qudrati oshdi. 1004-yildan Beruniyning Gurganchga kelishi bilan Xorazmshoh saroyida olimlar davrasi tezlik bilan to'la bordi va bu davrni Ma'mun akademiyasining to'la shakllangan, gullagan davri deyish mumkin. Abu Mansur as-Saolibiyning guvohlik berishicha, Gurganchda to'plangan faqat arabiynavis adiblarning o'zi 200 ga yaqin bo'lgan.

Tarixdan ayonki, vatanimizda taraqqiyotning yangi davri boshlanishi aynan Ma'mun asos solgan va Sharqning mashhur allomalarini bir dargohga jamlab, ularga zarur shart-sharoit, imkoniyat, imtiyozlar yaratib bergan 1004-yildagi "Dorul hikma", "Majlisi ulamo", ya'ni akademiya

tarqalgan ilm nurlaridan boshlanadi. Ma'munning hukmdor sifatidagi, davlat yuritishdagi huquq va siyosatdagi tafakkuri, ilm-fan namoyondalarini ezgu g'oyalar tevaragida birlashtirdi. Bu ezgu g'oya esa ko'p o'tmay jamiyatda o'z natijasini ko'rsatdi va matematika, astronomiya, kimyo, tibbiyot, huquq, geodeziya singari shu davrga xos barcha fanlar rivojlanib, Birinchi renessansga asos bo'ldi. Bunda o'z bag'riga daho mutafakkirlarni to'plagan oliy ma'rifat maskani – Ma'mun akademiyasi muhim rol o'ynagan edi.

Jahon ilm-u fanining e'tirof eshiticha, “Dor-ul hikma va maorif” (Ma'mun akademiyasi) nomini olgan mazkur ilmiy muassasa nafaqat Sharq balki butun dunyo uchun ham ahamiyatga egadir. Zeroki, ushbu dargohda Beruniy (973-1048), Ibn Sino (980-1037), Abu Mansur Ibn Iroq (958-1036), Abu Sahl Masihiy (970-1042), Abul Hayr Ibn Hammor (942-1018), Abu Mansur as-Saolibiy (961-1038), Abu Ali Ibn Miskovayh, (vafoti 1030), Abdulhakim Muhammad ibn Abdulmalik as-Solih, Al-Xorajiy, al-Hamdamiy, abu Abdulloh Al-Biyan Al-Naysaburiy, Ahmad Ibn Muhammad as-Suhayliy al-Xorazmiy, Ahmad ibn Muhammad as-Sahriy, Mahmud Hamid Ibn Xidr al-Xo'jandiy kabi ko'plab fan namoyandalari ilmiy tadqiqotlar olib borishgani, tarixiy fakt va ular yaratgan asarlar tamaddun taraqqiyoti tadrijida muhim o'rin egalladi.

Akademiyalar Yunoniston, Yaqin Sharq va Hindiston, O'rta Sharqda erishilgan ilm-fan yutuqlarini ijodiy, tanqidiy, qiyosiy tahlil qilib, uni yanada yuksak bosqichga ko'tarishgan. Aynan ana shu allomalarning ilmiy faoliyati, asarlari tufayli Qadimgi Xorazmning san'ati, adabiyoti, astronomiyasi, matematikasi, sug'orish madaniyati yutuqlari jahon tamadduni xazinasiga kirgan va butun insoniyat manfaatlariga xizmat qila boshlagan.

Mustaqillik yillarida tarixda chuqur iz qoldirgan tabarruk ilm dargohining qaytadan Xorazm zaminida barpo etilishi dunyo olimlari, ilm-fan jamoatchiligi tomonidan olqishlandi, iliq kutib olindi. YUNESKOning 2004-yilda “Xorazm Ma'mun akademiyasining 1000 yilligini nishonlash to'g'risida”gi qarori esa O'zbekiston hududi azaldan ilm-ma'rifat o'chog'i, ziyo markazi bo'lgani, bu an'ana bugun ham davom etayotganining jahoniy e'tirofi bo'ldi, albatta.

Davlatimiz rahbari Shavkat Mirziyoyevning 2017-yil yanvar oyida Xorazm viloyatiga, xususan, Xorazm Ma'mun akademiyasiga tashrifi davomida bergan topshiriq va ko'rsatmalari respublikamiz olimlariga ham ko'rsatilgan hurmat-ehtirom namunasidir. Tabiiyki, bu ajdodlarimiz qoldirgan bebaho ilmiy merosdan unumli foydalanish barobarida, ilmiy yangilik va kashfiyotlar qilish, innovatsiyalar yaratish, yoshlarni ilmga jalb etib, iqtidorli, dunyo tan oladigan yagi avlod olimlari yetishtirishga katta ishtiyoq uyg'otadi.

Bugungi kunda Xorazm ramziga aylangan Xiva shahri haqidagi ilk ma'lumotlar X asrga oid arab sayyohlari asarlarida uchrasada XVII asr boshlariga kelib yirik shaharga aylanadi. Xiva xonlari davrida davlatdagi ilm-fan, adabiyot va san'atga qiziqish yanada yuksaladi. Shaharda saroy, hovli, karvonsaroy, masjid, hammomlardan tashqari ilm, ma'rifat ulashguvchi madrasalar, qorixonalar, kichik yoshli bolalar uchun xususiy uy maktabxonalari qurila boshlandi. Bu jarayon, ayniqsa, XVII asrda nihoyatda avj olib, XIX asrda o'zining cho'qqisiga chiqdi. Xiva shahridan tashqari butun xonlik hududida katta va go'zal peshtoqli madrasalar, atrofi bir yo'la ikki qavatli hujralar bilan o'ralgan hovlisi, masjidi va minorasi bo'lgan madrasalar qurildi. Tarixiy ma'lumotlarga ko'ra, XIX asr boshlarida faqat Xiva shahrining o'zida 120 madrasa va 63 qorixona faoliyat olib borgan bo'lib, rus bosqinidan so'ng ular soni 64 taga, 1922-yilga kelib 54 taga kamayganligini ko'rish mumkin. Mazkur madrasalarda islom dini va huquqidan tashqari, arab va fors tillari, tibbiyot, geografiya, musiqashunoslik, falsafa, tabiiy bilimlar kabi dunyoviy fanlar o'rgatilar edi. Madrasalar davlat idoralari uchun mutaxassislar, maktabdor va san'atkorlarni tayyorlab berdi.

Mustaqillik sharofati bilan Xorazmda ilm-fanga bo'lgan e'tibor yaxshilandi. XI asrda faoliyat olib borgan “Majlis ul-ulamo”ning vorisi sifatida Xiva shahrida Xorazm Ma'mun akademiyasi 1997-yil 11-noyabrda Birinchi Prezidentning maxsus farmoni asosida qayta tashkil qilingan bo'lsa, 2006-yilda uning 1000 yillik yubileyi keng miqyosda nishonlandi. Mazkur tadqiqot muassasasining ochilishi Xorazmda tarix, arxeologiya, manbashunoslik, filologiya, tuproqshunoslik, qishloq xo'jaligi kabi mintaqa uchun zarur bilimlarning rivojiga ta'sir qildi. Jumladan, 2500 yildan ortiq tarixga ega bo'lgan Xumbuztepa arxeologik yodgorligining ochilishi va uning quyi qatlamlari miloddan avvalgi VII-VI asrlarga oidligi isbotlanganining o'zi fikrimizning yaqqol misolidir.

Yuqorida ta'kidlanganidek, ulkan ilmiy meros va tarixga ega bo'lgan Xorazm va uning ajralmas bir qismi hisoblangan Xiva shahrida bugungi kunda ham ilm-fanga e'tibor yildan yilga ortib bormoqda. Xivada tashkil qilingan Ma'mun universiteti ulkan ilmiy salohiyatning mantiqiy davomi sifatida faoliyatini boshlaganiga hali ko'p bo'lgani yo'q.

Dunyo afkor ommasining e'tibor va e'tirofiga ega bo'lgan hamda shu davrda yaratilgan boqiy asarlari bilan hanuz tamaddunga xizmat qilib kelayotgan olimlarni o'z dargohiga to'plagan, ilm-fan homiysi, o'z davrining Metsenati hisoblangan, ma'rifatparvar Ma'mun nomi bilan ataladigan universitet qisqa davr ichida respublikada o'z nufuziga, obro-e'tiboriga ega bo'ldi. Muassasa yildan yilga o'z maqomini mustahkamlab borayotgani kishini quvontiradi.

Ushbu ta'lim dargohi bugungi kunda 7 mingga yaqin talablar tahsil olayotgan, Xiva shahrida faoliyat olib borayotgan dastlabki va hozircha yagona zamonaviy universitet sifatida o'z mustahkam o'rniga ega bo'lib ulgurdi. Bugungi kunda universitetda ikki yuzdan ortiq malakali professor-o'qituvchilar (shundan yuzga yaqini ilmiy darajali) ta'lim jarayonlari bilan bir vaqtda o'zlarining ilmiy faoliyatlarini Xorazm Ma'mun akademiyasi va boshqa ilmiy tashkilotlar bilan hamnafas, hamkorlikda olib borishmoqda.

Mamlakatda xususiy oliy ta'lim muassasalarining ochilishi nafaqat oliy ta'lim muassasalari o'rtasidagi raqobatni kuchaytirishga, balki hududlarning iqtisodiy ahvoriga ham o'z ta'sirini kuchaytiradi. Xususan, hozirgi kunda Oliy ta'lim, fan va innovatsiyalar vazirligi ma'lumotlariga ko'ra, bugungi kunda mamlakatimizda 210 ta OTM mavjud bo'lib, undan 65 tasi nodavlat oliy ta'lim muassasalari bo'lsa, 30 tasi xorijiy oliy ta'lim muassasalari va ularning filiallari hisoblanadi. Bundan ko'rishimiz mumkinki, mamlakatimizdagi jami oliy ta'lim muassasalarining deyarli yarmi nodavlat va xorijiy oliy ta'lim muassasalari hissasiga to'g'ri keladi. Bu, albatta, quvonarli holat, ya'ni abituriyentlarga keng tanlov imkoniyati yaratildi. Nodavlat oliy ta'lim muassasalarining faoliyat olib borishi oliy o'quv yurtlari o'rtasida nafaqat talabalarni o'ziga jalb etish uchun raqobatni rivojlantirdi, balki ilmiy salohiyatli va bilimli bo'lgan professor-o'qituvchilarni o'ziga jalb etish bo'yicha ham o'zaro raqobat muhiti shakllandi. Natijada, o'qituvchilik kasbining maqomi oshdi, uning qadri ko'tarildi, ish haqlari oshirildi, ularga bo'lgan munosabat o'zgardi, eng asosiysi, o'qituvchilarda o'z-o'ziga ishonch, kasbiga bo'lgan ichki hurmat tuyg'usi mustahkamlandi, ilmiy tadqiqot olib borish uchun ijodiy muhit sifati yaxshilanib, natijada ishtiyoq oshdi.

Mamlakatimizdagi nodavlat oliy ta'lim muassasalari faoliyat olib borishi uchun yaratilgan sharoitlar va berilayotgan imkoniyatlar natijasida nafaqat poytaxtimizda, balki hududlarda ham nodavlat oliy ta'lim muassasalari o'z faoliyatini boshladi va buning natijasida hududlarning iqtisodiyoti, aholining turmush darajasi, turizm salohiyati, investitsion jozibadorligi oshdi. Xususan, davlat rahbarimiz boshchiligida ta'lim muassasalari va pedagog-xodimlarga yaratilayotgan sharoitlar va imkoniyatlar natijasida Xorazm viloyatida ham nodavlat oliy ta'lim muassasalarining faoliyat olib borishi uchun yetarli sharoitlar va imkoniyatlar yaratildi va buning natijasida hozirga kunda viloyatda 3 ta nodavlat oliy ta'lim muassasalari va 1 ta xorijiy oliy ta'lim muassasasi filiali faoliyat olib bormoqda.

Ma'mun universiteti viloyatdagi oliy ta'lim muassasalari orasida talabalar kontingenti bo'yicha 2-o'rinda (1-o'rinda UrDU), nodavlat oliy ta'lim muassasalari orasida esa 1-o'rinda turadi. Ma'mun universitetining asosiy binosi viloyat markazidan 30-35 km. masofa uzoqlikda joylashganligiga qaramasdan, hozirgi kunda ushbu universitetda 7 mingdan ortiq talaba kunduzgi va sirtqi ta'lim shakllarida tahsil olib kelmoqda. Yana bir quvonarli tomoni shundaki, universitet talabalari tarkibi nafaqat viloyatimiz aholisidan, balki respublikamizning deyarli barcha hududlari aholisidan tashkil topgan. Viloyatimizda bunday oliy ta'lim muassasasining faoliyat olib borishi nafaqat yoshlarning oliy ta'lim bilan qamrab olish darajasini oshishiga olib keladi, balki ularning bilimi, fikrlashi, dunyoqarashi kengayishiga olib keladi, hududning madaniy-maishiy saviyasiga ijobiy ta'sir ko'rsatadi.

Hududlarda nodavlat oliy ta'lim muassasalarining faoliyat olib borishi iqtisodiy jihatdan bevosita o'sha hududning rivojlanishiga, yalpi ichki mahsulot hajmining oshishiga, aholi bandligini oshishiga, aholi turmush tarzining oshishi, hududlarda xizmat ko'rsatish sohasi faoliyati, turizm faoliyatining rivojlanishiga olib keladi. Ma'mun universitetining Xiva shahrida faoliyat olib borishi

natijasida, nafaqat tumanning, balki viloyatning iqtisodiy-ijtimoiy ahvoriga o'zining ijobiy hissasini qo'shib kelmoqda. Jumladan, universitet faoliyat olib borishi natijasida ikki yuz ellikdan ortiq yangi ish o'rinlari ochildi, universitetga har yili 20 dan ortiq xorijlik professor-o'qituvchilarning jalb etilishi natijasida turistik xizmatlar hajmi oshdi, respublikaning boshqa hududlaridan professor-o'qituvchilar va talabalarning jalb etilishi natijasida ichki turizm rivojlandi, hududdagi savdo va xizmat ko'rsatish sohalari deyarli 1,5-2 barobarga oshdi, xorijlik ilmiy salohiyatli olimlarni jalb etish orqali xorijiy mamlakatlar bilan hamkorlik aloqalari rivojlanishiga erishildi.

Eng samarali reklama insonlarning yaqinlariga qilgan reklamasi (jonli reklama) ekanligini hisobga olgan holda, viloyatimizga, universitetimizga tashrif buyurgan har bir mehmonda universitetimiz faoliyati, viloyatimiz, respublikamiz iqtisodiyoti, aholi turmush darajasi, urf-odatlarini, tarixiy obidalarini, bayramlari, ovqatlari haqida ijobiy xulosalarni shakllantirishga erishsak, kelajakda ular nafaqat ta'lim berish uchun, balki o'z yaqinlari bilan birga dam olish maqsadida ham tashrif buyurishlari mumkin.

Universitet oldiga qo'ygan asosiy maqsadlardan biri bu – barcha talabalarni to'liq grant asosida, bepul o'qitish tizimini joriy etish, dunyoning eng rivojlangan oliy o'quv yurtlari mingtaligiga kirish va Ma'mun universiteti brendini yaratish, Ma'mun ta'lim klasterini joriy etish hisoblanadi. Bu borada universitetimizda bir qator ishlab olib borilmoqda va "Ma'mun universiteti-2030" strategiyasi bo'yicha yo'l xaritalari ishlab chiqildi. Bunday natijalarga universitetda "Universitet 3.0" modelini to'liq joriy etish va bosqichma-bosqich "Universitet 4.0" modeliga o'tish orqali erishish rejalashtirilgan.

Ushbu ko'zlangan maqsadlarga erishmaguncha universitet jamoasi izlanishdan, harakatdan, ilm olishdan, ilm o'rgatishdan to'xtamaymiz va rejalarni amaliyotga joriy etish orqali, mamlakatimiz rahbarining, talabalarning, xalqimizning oldidagi majburiyatimizni bajargan va ularning ishonchini oqlagan bo'lamiz.

Barchamizga ma'lumki, har qanday jamiyatning ravnaqi, ijtimoiy, siyosiy, iqtisodiy barqarorligi o'sha yerda istiqomat qiluvchi fuqarolarining aqliy va axloqiy salohiyatining qay darajada rivojlanganligi bilan bog'liq. Zero, jamiyatning ma'naviy kamoloti, ijtimoiy yashash tarzi, kognitiv rivojlanganlik darajasi shu davlatning milliy mentaliteti yuksalishida, shuningdek, kadrlar tayyorlashning milliy masalasida ham ustuvor mezon hisoblanadi. Inson kamolotida, uning farovonligi va shaxsiy manfaatlarini ro'yobga chiqarishda hamda kerakli ijtimoiy xulq-atvor andozalarini shakllantirishda kasbning ahamiyati katta hisoblanadi. Ayniqsa, bugungi kunda rivojlanayotgan psixolog mutaxassislariga bo'lgan talab davr talabi sifatida yaqqol namoyon bo'lmoqda. Inson bolasi kamolga yetgani sari ilmga, ma'rifatga talpinadi. Shu nuqtayi nazardan saboqni doimiy ravishda ijtimoiy muhit ta'sirida o'zlashtirib boradi. Bugungi shiddatkor jamiyatda psixolog kasbiga bo'lgan talab aynan inson omili bilan ishlashda, uning ta'sir obyektining butun hayotidagi ahamiyatini hisobga oladigan bo'lsak, shaxs kamolotida turli xil muammolarning yuzaga kelishi va uning yechimi bilan faoliyat olib borishda ko'rinadi.

Jamiyatda shaxsning shakllanishi insonning o'z aqliy qobiliyatlari jismoniy imkoniyatlari u yoki bu sohaga bo'lgan layoqati, qiziqish va intilishlari, shuningdek, qadriyat va dunyoqarashiga ko'ra belgilanar ekan, inson omilining aynan shu jihatlarni shakllanishi va rivojlanishida salbiy omillarning ta'sirini bo'lmasligini cheklay olmaymiz, chunki hayot tarzi turli xillik bilan bog'liqligidan tashqari, inson shaxsi rivojlanishidagi ehtiyojlari, individual psixologik xususiyatlari, atrof-muhit ta'siri kabilar murakkab hayot tarzining dolzarb muammolaridan biridir.

Bu o'rinda Ma'mun universiteti o'z oldiga psixolog kasbiga tayyorlanadigan mutaxassislarni har tomonlama yetuk, eng avvalo, boshqalarga yordam berish ko'nikmasini shakllantirish bilan birga o'z shaxsiy muammolarini oldindan ko'ra bilish va uni hal qila olish imkoniyatiga ega bo'lgan mutaxassislarni tayyorlashni o'z oldiga maqsad qilib qo'ygan. Chunki, inson shaxsida, turli yoshdagi kishilar bo'lgan jamoaviy munosabatlarda, kasbiy faoliyatga moslashish, yangi ijtimoiy rolni tushunib olish har bir inson hayotida yangi muammolarni keltirib chiqarishini hisobga olgan holda bu mezonlarga e'tibor qaratish hamda jahon amaliyotining muhim ahamiyatga ega bo'lgan, shuningdek, zamon talablariga mos keladigan jahon andozalari asosida mutaxassislikka tayyorlashga alohida e'tibor qaratilmoqda.

O‘zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti Shavkat Mirziyoyev tashabbusi bilan jamiyatimizda amalga oshirilayotgan islohotlar, tabiiyki inson qadrini oshirish, uning huquq va manfaatlari himoyasini kuchaytirishdek ezgu maqsadga yo‘naltirilgan. Aynan shu tufayli ham davlat rahbarining siyosiy irodasi bois huquqiy demokratik, adolatli jamiyatda, ilm-u fan rivoji uchun ilmiy-pedagogik jamoalarga zarur shart-sharoit, imkoniyat yaratib berilmoqda. Negaki, davlatimiz rahbari ta’kidlaganlaridek, “Biz o‘z oldimizga mamlakatimizda Uchinchi Renessans poydevorini barpo etishdek ulug‘ maqsadni qo‘ygan ekanmiz, buning uchun yangi xorazmiylar, beruniylar, ibn sinolar, ulug‘beklar, Navoiy va boburlarni tarbiyalab beradigan muhit va sharoitlarni yaratishimiz kerak”, degan da’vatiga hamohang olib borilayotgan tizimli yangilanishlarning amaldagi in’ikosidir.

Agarki tarixdagi jarayonlarga nazar solib, tahlil etadigan bo‘lsak, davlat boshqaruvida olib borilgan odil siyosat, davlatning ilm-ma’rifatga, olimlarga e’tibori, ta’lim-tarbiya ustuvor etib qo‘yilgani o‘tmishdagi Uyg‘onish davriga xos eng muhim jihat bo‘lgan.

Aynan shu ma’noda, so‘nggi yillarda Yangi O‘zbekistonda amalga oshirilayotgan islohotlarni, ayniqsa, ilm-fan, ta’lim sohadagi innovatsion yangilanishlar, olim va ziyolilarga yaratib berilayotgan shart-sharoitlar, yoshlar ta’lim-tarbiyasi yo‘lida bajarilayotgan beqiyos ishlarni ma’rifatparvar Xorazmshoh Ma’moni ibn Ma’mun, Ali ibn Ma’munning, adolatparvar Sohibqiron Amir Temurning tamoyillariga qiyoslash mumkin. Ya’ni, bugungi davrimizda o‘tmish bilan bugun va kelajak uyg‘unlashgan holda yana Renessanslarga xos tamaddunga zamin yaratilmoqda.

Shu ma’noda Ma’mun universitetining o‘tmishdagi Ma’mun asos solgan, rivoj toptirgan akademiyasi singari dovruc tarqatishi borasidagi o‘z sa’yi harakatlarimizda dadil boraveramiz.

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E-mail.: fereh7@mail.ru**ARMENIA-AZERBAIJAN CONFLICT: HISTORY AND REALITIES** <http://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10028812>**ABSTRACT**

The migration of Armenians to the Caucasus is connected with the historically multifaceted policy of European countries. From time to time, the states that raised the Armenian issues have benefited from wars, diplomatic and economic pressures for the purpose of its realization depending on the circumstances. Among the actions taken by the states trying to take advantage of the Armenian issue, the most effective use of national minorities in the Ottoman Empire and sectarian divisions within Christianity also played an important role. From this point of view, the Armenian issue can be assessed as a multifaceted international policy. The views and positions that try to "justify" the emergence of the Armenian issue with their deplorable situation in Turkey and Azerbaijan, as well as various pressures, are fundamentally wrong.

At the same time, today's Armenian claims are closely linked to the "Eastern Question", which has been part of the system of international relations since the late 18th century. The Ottoman Empire was chosen as the main target of the "Eastern Question". The process of the collapse of the Ottoman Empire accelerated in the 19th century due to various factors. The states that created the "Eastern problem" have brought this problem to a greater level by identifying various methods and means for its "solution".

Key words: Azerbaijan territory, the Armenian issue , "Eastern Problem", genocide, Nagorny Karabakh, Armenia.

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ARMAN-OZARBAYJON MOJAROSI: TARIX VA HAQIQAT**ANNOTATSIYA**

Armanlarning Kavkazga ko'chishi Yevropa davlatlarining tarixan ko'p qirrali siyosati bilan bog'liq. Vaqti-vaqti bilan arman masalasini ko'targan davlatlar sharoitga qarab, uni amalga oshirish uchun urushlardan, diplomatik va iqtisodiy bosimlardan foydalandi. Arman masalasidan foydalanishga harakat qilgan davlatlarning harakatlari orasida Usmonlilar imperiyasidagi milliy ozchiliklardan samarali foydalanish va nasroniylik ichidagi mazhabiy farqlar ham muhim rol o'ynadi. Shu nuqtai nazardan qaraganda, Armaniston masalasini ko'p qirrali xalqaro siyosat sifatida baholash mumkin. Armanlarning Turkiya va Ozarbayjondagi ayanchli ahvoli, turli tazyiqlar bilan arman masalasining paydo bo'lishini "oqlashga" urinayotgan qarashlar va pozitsiyalar tubdan noto'g'ri.

Shu bilan birga, Armanistonning hozirgi da'volari XVIII asrning oxiridan beri xalqaro munosabatlar tizimining bir qismi bo'lgan "Sharqiy masala" bilan chambarchas bog'liq. Sharqiy masalasining asosiy maqsadi sifatida Usmonli imperiyasi tanlandi. XIX asrda turli omillar ta'sirida Usmonli imperiyasining parchalanish jarayoni tezlashdi. "Sharq muammosi"ni yaratgan davlatlar bu muammoni "hal qilish"ning turli uslub va vositalarini belgilab, yuqori darajaga ko'tardilar.

Kalit so'zlar: Ozarbayjon hududi, Arman masalasi, "Sharq muammosi", genotsid, Tog'li Qorabog', Armaniston.

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АРМЯНО-АЗЕРБАЙДЖАНСКИЙ КОНФЛИКТ: ИСТОРИЯ И РЕАЛИИ**АННОТАЦИЯ**

Миграция армян на Кавказ связана с исторически многогранной политикой европейских стран. Время от времени государства, поднявшие армянский вопрос, в зависимости от обстоятельств извлекали выгоду из войн, дипломатического и экономического давления с целью его реализации. Среди действий государств, пытавшихся воспользоваться армянским вопросом, важную роль также сыграло наиболее эффективное использование национальных меньшинств в Османской империи и сектантских разногласий внутри христианства. С этой точки зрения армянский вопрос можно оценить как многогранную международную политику. Взгляды и позиции, которые пытаются «оправдать» возникновение армянского вопроса их плачевным положением в Турции и Азербайджане, а также различным давлением, в корне неверны.

В то же время сегодняшние претензии Армении тесно связаны с «Восточным вопросом», который является частью системы международных отношений с конца XVIII века. Османская империя была выбрана в качестве основной цели «Восточного вопроса». Процесс распада Османской империи ускорился в XIX веке из-за различных факторов. Государства, создавшие «восточную проблему», вывели эту проблему на более высокий уровень, определив различные методы и средства ее «решения».

Ключевые слова: территория Азербайджана, армянский вопрос, «Восточная проблема», геноцид, Нагорный Карабах, Армения.

INTRODUCTION.

The Armenian problem is a part of the "Eastern issue"

The "Armenian question", considered the work of Europeans, was raised in the second half of the 19th century, mainly after the Russian-Turkish War of 1877-1878 by Russia, England and the Church. This problem found its first official expression in the 16th Article of the Treaty of San Stefano. And relating to this issue the 61th Article of the Berlin Treaty became the current subject of international relations.

Western countries began to promote the Armenian issue more widely in the name of protecting Christians. They unhesitatingly invented an Armenian issue in Turkey, exaggerating the ideas of Armenian nationalism. However, all this served the purpose of taking a share of Turkey's historical heritage. In fact, Europe was not interested in the real desires of the Armenians.

After a while, the demands of the Armenians for autonomy in the lands belonging to the Ottoman state became widespread. The demands and aspirations of the Armenian clergy, which exceeded the limits and were already materialized by the statesmen of the tsar, were met with sharp and justified protests of the Ottoman peace mission. Ottoman diplomats stated that they would not accept the condition of the independence of the Armenians in connection with these intentions and a specific article without the consent of the sultan. Thereby, the aspirations of the Armenians for autonomy were unequivocally rejected[1].

METHODS AND THE LEVEL OF STUDY.

The overview the recent research and publications.

The author reviews the monograph of Svante E. Cornell, "Autonomy and Conflict: Caucasian Conflicts in Theoretical Perspective" (2002), Hacıyeva A. "Beynəlxalq Münasibətlər Tarixi" (1871-1919) (Bakı-2003) and analyzes Əhmədov E. "Ermənistanın Azərbaycanca təcavüzü və beynəlxalq təşkilatlar" (Bakı, 1998) in the article.

The used methods in the article.

The methodological basis of the article is based on the basic provisions and categories of the theory of dialectics and cognition, learning the general development of nations. Using historical analysis method, the author researched the occasional resettlement of Armenians from Western countries to the ancient lands of Azerbaijan. In the study, as a result of comparative and systematic analysis of Azerbaijan-Armenia relations it was noted that the historical claims of the Armenians became a reality in illegal and insidious ways.

The scientific innovation

The Armenian problem, which has gone down in history as part of the "Eastern question", is a product of European political goals. Taking advantage of such opportunities, the Armenians began to settle in small groups in Eastern Anatolia and the Caucasus. European states, as well as Russia have always used them as intermediary weapons for their own purposes. As a result, the Armenians occupied the historical lands of Azerbaijan and did not back down from their claims to the Nagorno-Karabakh region.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS.

Around this time, there was a process that would create favorable conditions for the transportation and promotion of the problems of Armenians in Europe. So, from that time onwards, the influx of missionaries from different Christian churches began to the Ottoman Empire. The activities of Christian missionaries also created sectarian divisions in the Armenian Gregorian Church and deepened this division. Moreover, the owners of sects (Gregorian, Catholic, Orthodox, Protestant) and political beliefs (Dashnak, Communist, etc.) did not separate, on the contrary, they united in the cause of the "Greater Armenia".

In order to "save Armenia", the missionaries gave the Christian states the opportunity to interfere in the internal affairs of the Ottoman Empire. Armenian missionaries played the role of ideological and propaganda base of the Armenian issue in the Ottoman Empire with the policy of "protection of Christians". It was as a result of the missionaries' activities that the Christian subjects provided organizational, financial, and military assistance.

And in this direction, from about the 16th century, Armenian clergymen purposefully worked. This was confirmed by all Armenian clergymen in 1541, from Stepan, who was elected Catholicos

of Echmiadzin. It is noted that the Armenian patriarch of Istanbul M. Hirimyan put forward the idea of creating an autonomous Armenia within the Ottoman state.

It is also known from the history of Christianity that during the fall of the Byzantine Empire by Sultan Mehmed the Conqueror, there were three Armenian patriarchates (Gregorians in Jerusalem and Echmiadzin, and Catholics in Kilikya)[2].

The establishment of another Gregorian patriarchate by Fatih in Istanbul played an important role in the organization, socialization and, in general, the future of the Armenians. Thus, during the centuries-old Byzantine period, the Armenian patriarchate was never allowed in Constantinople, there was only one Armenian church in the city. It was during his visit to Jerusalem on November 9, 1517, that they were given sufficient rights and privileges by the historical decree of Sultan Salim Yavuz, who was met on the outskirts of the city by the Armenian patriarch Sarkis III and others.

However, in spite of all this, the Armenian Church, in accordance with its historical goals and from time to time in response to various external influences, has been intensifying its anti-Ottoman activities since the 16th century. Armenian clerics, on behalf of their "suffering compatriots", began to knock on the doors of the so-called spokesmen of the time and demanded a "solution to their problems." There were plans for ways to get rid of Muslim rule, and for this purpose a delegation was sent to the capitals of European countries, the Papacy. But this mission had failed.

Numerous documents in the Ottoman archives of the Prime Minister's Office also indicate the anti-state actions of Armenians in various regions in the 16th century. For example: Van Beylerbeys - Pashas: According to Hussein and Alexander's information to the Divan, about a thousand Armenians gathered for three days and decided to commit corruption.

The services of Mkhitarists in bringing the "Armenian consciousness" to Europe are undeniable. This sect, founded by the Ottoman (Sivas) Armenian Mkhitar, carried out extensive propaganda through its institutions in Europe. Mkhitar, who wanted to unite the Armenian patriarchate with the Roman Church, together with his followers wrote many books about Armenians and distributed them in European countries. They also established a monastery on the island of St. Lazarus, given by the Senate of the Republic of Venice. This religious organization later began to function as the "Armenian Academy".

These events prompted the Armenian clergy to establish intensive relations with the tsar (Peter I). Thus, the return of Peter I from the march to the Caspian region, the treaties he signed with the Safavids and the Ottoman Empire (St. Petersburg - 1723, Istanbul - 1724) revealed the policy of the empire on the Armenian issue. Peter I did not establish a separate "Armenian state" in the lands of Azerbaijan, but only organized the migration of Armenians to the newly occupied territories[3].

Armenian clerics also tried to take advantage of Russia's military successes in the Caucasus in the early 19th century and their geopolitical consequences. One of the main ideologues and organizers of this work was the Catholicos of the Three Churches (Echmiadzin) Nerses Ashtaraketsi. Catholicos N. Ashtaraketsi played a great role in the division of the Azerbaijani khanates during the Russian-Iranian wars.

During and after the occupation of the Caucasus, the Russian state took a number of political and diplomatic measures to capture Armenians (especially religious leaders) who lived in Gajar and Ottoman states. Achieving the inclusion of Article 15 in the Turkmenchay Treaty, the Russian government extended the rights granted to Orthodox Russians to Gregorian Armenians. Taking advantage of such privileges, Armenians began to demand the abolition of the Albanian Catholicosate. As a result, the Russian government exiled Catholicos Nerses Ashtaraketsi to Bessarabia for life to avoid the Catholicos' plans for independence.

Britain's position on the "East Question" was significant. The political purpose of Britain's use of the Armenians in the implementation of its plans for the Ottoman Empire was very important. This was also positively influenced by the Ottoman's unparalleled tolerance for all religious beliefs and the favorable conditions created for missionary activities within its borders. The English Protestant missionary activity, which covered a large system, from the distribution of Armenian Gospels to the organization of free education, soon bore fruit. As a result of the deepening of sectarian divisions between Armenians and so on. The British government was able to repel the resistance of the Russian

embassy and the Armenian patriarchate in Istanbul. The West, especially Britain, which demanded greater rights for Ottoman Christians, attributed this to their "difficult situation." As a result, by a special decree of the sultan (1859), Protestant Armenians received the status of a separate religious community. One of the Armenian religious sects in the Ottoman Empire (Gregorian and Catholic) was added (Protestant)[4].

It is possible to come to such a conclusion, which is quite reasonable. The Ottoman government created the same (equal) conditions for all Armenian religions, regardless of their religion. And the Protestant Armenians, protected by the Anglo-Americans, were no exception.

In Eastern policy, the Russian government worked closely with the Armenians to gain control of the Straits and access to hot water. During the wars of 1804-1813 and 1826-1828, which resulted in the division of Azerbaijan between Russia and Iran, Armenians preferred betrayal. During the Russian occupation of a number of Azerbaijani khanates, the small group of Armenians sided with the occupying army. The Russian state, in turn, did not leave the services of Armenians free. So he created an "Armenian province" in the occupied territories of Azerbaijan - in the territories of the former Iravan and Nakhchivan khanates (3.1828).

However, although Russia was active in the resettlement of Armenians to the territories of Azerbaijan, it never agreed to the establishment of the Armenian state within the borders of the empire. For this reason, the Armenians tried to realize their dream of building a "Greater Armenia" in Eastern Anatolia.

Russian writer and journalist SN Glinka in his book "Description of the resettlement of Azerbaijani Armenians in Russia" (1831), published by Lazarevs in Moscow, shows that Peter I did not want to overlook the Armenians. He wanted to involve them in useful work for Russia. During his visit to Iran, the "Great Reformer Peter" personally witnessed the unshakable loyalty of the Armenian people in his own experience, and later invited the "loyal" Armenians to Russia as useful citizens.

The author notes that in order to stage Russian affairs in the Caucasus, but in fact to exert political and psychological influence on the Armenians, General Paskevich was instructed to invite Colonel Lazarev to the Caucasus Corps, because the very appearance of this official among the Armenians "worthy" was the embodiment of Russia's sympathy for his sons.

The role of the active participation of Armenians in trade relations between Iran and Russia in the rapprochement of Armenian nationalists with Russia was unprecedented. Adhering to the principle of "trade is politics", they seized Russian officials with expensive gifts and bribes, laying the real foundation for future political relations and diplomatic negotiations. They almost achieved their "national" goals[5].

The transfer of the Garabakh khanate to the Russian protectorate by the Kurakchay Treaty of 1805 was in fact the first legal document marking the beginning of Russia's occupation of Azerbaijan. The policy of resettlement of Armenians in the territory of Garabakh began due to the fact that the Russians had more opportunities in the region and through the mediation of Russia. In the 1820s, Armenians made up only 8.4% of the local population, but after the Turkmenchay Treaty of 1828, the number of Armenians increased. As a result of mass relocations to the Garabakh region, Azeri Turks accounted for 64.8% and Armenians for 34.8%.

The sharp change in the demographic situation in the region, in fact, created the most favorable conditions for strengthening the colonial geopolitics of Russian tsarism. In the example of the Armenian communities, the Russian state created a social base in accordance with its strategic goals, and using the Christian factor, tsarism expanded its colonial policy against the Muslim population at the hands of "loyal Armenians. "As a result of resettlement to the Caucasus, especially to the ancient lands of Azerbaijan (İrevan, Nakhchivan, Zangazur, Garabakh), only between 1828 and 1830, about 130,000 Armenians moved in this direction.

Also, according to Article 15 of the Turkmenchay Treaty, more than 40,000 Armenians were relocated to İrevan, Nakhchivan, Garabakh, Zangazur and Ganja regions of Azerbaijan in a short period of time. The proportion of Armenians in the total population of Garabakh increased from 8.4

percent in 1823 to 34.8 percent in 1832. During this period, more than 1 million of the 1.3 million Armenians living in the South Caucasus were deported by Russia[6].

The formation of the Armenian province (1828) and then the İrevan province (1850) in a part of the lands of Northern Azerbaijan, which joined the Russian Empire, should be considered as the first embryos of the modern problems facing the Azerbaijani state.

In the 1970s, Western countries planned to influence Ottoman state and interfere in its internal affairs by raising the Armenian issue.

The inclusion of the "Armenian issue" in Article 16 of the Treaty of San Stefano was made possible by the strong efforts of the Armenian Patriarchate, civil servants and Russian diplomats. Article 16 of the Treaty of San Stefano stated: "Given that the withdrawal of Russian troops from the territories inhabited by Armenians and the return of these territories to the Ottoman state, could lead to clashes in those territories, which could negatively affect the good relations between the two countries. The Great Port undertakes to carry out reforms in the Armenian-populated areas without delay, as well as to ensure the security of the latter from the Kurds and Circassians".

According to the agreement, in order to improve the situation and ensure the security of the Armenians, the sultan's government had to carry out reforms in the eastern provinces inhabited by Armenians (where 20-40 percent of the population were Armenians). According to this peace agreement, Turkey was forced to agree on three main issues - there is a country called Armenia, whose governance needs reform. Security is being violated by the Kurds and Circassians.

Russia wanted to Balkanize Eastern Anatolia, including strategic points such as Batumi and Kars, and strengthen its influence over Turkey. Russia was not interested in establishing an independent Armenian state in Turkey by uniting Eastern Anatolia with İrevan and Nakhchivan. Because it was not in line with his Armenian policy without Armenians. Russia added Article 16 to the agreement in order to please the Armenians and strengthen its influence in Turkey.

It was not accidental that the Armenian issue, which had nothing to do with the peace agreement, was included in the agreement as a separate article. First, Western capital viewed the Armenians, especially the Armenian bourgeoisie, as their economic intermediaries in Turkey. Instead, the Armenian bourgeoisie posed the task of reforming the eastern provinces inhabited by Armenians and forcing the Turkish state to do so. The main goal of the Armenians was to determine their own destiny, that is, to achieve the establishment of an autonomous entity belonging to the Armenians in the eastern provinces of Turkey. Article 16 of the San Stefano Peace Treaty was the first step in this direction. Second, to weaken Turkey's influence in the area between the Mediterranean and the Persian Gulf, which is of great strategic importance. This could be achieved with the help of Armenians living here. During this period, the growing movement under the slogan "Struggle for the liberation of Christians from Turkish-Muslim oppression" served this purpose. Third was the Muslim and Christian factor. By defending the Armenians, the goal of the western states was to bring the straits out of the control of the Muslim Turks and into the control of the Christian Armenians. So the Armenian issue was a political, national and religious issue.

Article 61 of the Berlin Treaty stated: "The High Port carries out the necessary reforms in the area inhabited by Armenians and ensures the security of the Armenians from the Kurds and Circassians. He must constantly inform the major powers about the work he is doing for this purpose"[7].

After the Berlin conference, Armenian separatist tendencies intensified in Turkey.

Unfounded territorial claims of Armenia against Azerbaijan

A very important diplomatic document from the early twentieth century addresses these issues. Thus, in a report sent to the Minister of Foreign Affairs of his country by the German Ambassador to Istanbul Wangenheim on June 10, 1913, he expressed his views and opinions on the Armenian issue:

- The Armenian movement is a means for Russia to keep its Asian Turkey in a state of constant excitement and, in due course, to hold it in a position that will make it possible for it to intervene as a neighboring state;

- Russia wants to keep the road to Istanbul open with the help of the Armenian issue. This is a key that will open their throats when the time comes for him.

The British diplomat E. Grenville wrote that "before the Russian provocation, there was no Armenian movement in the Ottoman Empire and innocent people suffered because of dreams like Armenia under the auspices of the tsar"[8].

During this period, new projects emerged for the Armenians to gain independence and create a state. One of such projects was prepared by the Armenian spiritual politician-Catholicos H. Argutyan of the second half of the XVIII century.

It should be noted that, there are as H.Aknuni's "Caucasian Wounds" (Tbilisi, 1905), Monk Agatyan's "Armenian Historical Divan" (Book IV, Tbilisi, 1899, pp.731-737), Leon's "Armenian Question" documents "(Tbilisi, 1915).

It was as a result of the Western countries' exaggeration of the Armenian issue that the Armenians, who had lived peacefully in these places for more than 500 years, rose up, began to think about gaining the support of Western countries, and became more active. Great Britain opened its consulates in Trabzon, Erzurum, Van, Bitlis and Diyarbakir. The British held meetings with representatives of the Kurdish and Armenian parties and formed mixed associations in order to strengthen their position among the Armenians. As a result of the joint activities of the Anglo-Armenian society established in 1882, Armenians committed the Armenian-Muslim massacre in 1894-1896. While Germany defended Turkey for its economic and military interests, the governments of France, Russia, and Italy were interested in tearing the Ottoman Empire apart[9].

The turmoil in the Russian Empire in the early twentieth century created ample opportunities for the restoration of a "Greater Armenia." Taking advantage of these events, the Armenians pursued the first Turkish-Muslim genocide policy within its borders.

At the All-Armenian National Congress in Tbilisi (Georgia) in 1913, strategic goals and tactical lines were defined. The goal was to be recognized as a people fighting on the side of the Entente. The strategic goal was to gain a large share of the Ottoman partition as an Entente partner if the war ended in favor of the Allies.

The political situation in Russia after the February Revolution and the international conditions of the time gave a new impetus to the claims of "Greater Armenia". Taking advantage of the opportunity, the Armenians, trying to seize the Caspian and Black Sea territories, further expanded their baseless claims to Azerbaijani lands.

According to the tactics chosen for the implementation of the "Greater Armenia" strategy, the Armenians promoted the implementation of the policy of Turkish-Muslim genocide (ethnic cleansing, burnt land) in Azerbaijan. From the beginning of 1917 to March 1918, 197 Muslim villages in the Iravan province were destroyed and vacated. 135,000 Turkish-Muslims living here were slaughtered and expelled.

Both the provision of the territorial integrity of Azerbaijan in 1918-1919 and the prevention of violence against its Turkish-Muslim population conditioned the Azerbaijan Democratic Republic to take urgent and serious political-diplomatic-military measures. The diplomacy of the Azerbaijan Democratic Republic has given priority to the settlement of territorial and border issues in order to prevent large-scale political and military conflicts in the South Caucasus and to establish interstate relations. As a result, on May 29, 1918, the National Council of Azerbaijan made a wrong decision to recognize İrevan as the political center of the Republic of Armenia. The ADR government justified such a concession on the basis of historical necessity, the possibility of establishing a confederation between the two countries in the future, as well as to deter Armenians from other territorial claims against Azerbaijan. Of course, it is not right to justify the concession of İrevan, the historical land of Azerbaijan, to the Armenians. Because after this incident, territorial claims became more acute.

The violence against the Turkish-Muslim population continued, and the possibility of a confederation was replaced by the reality of war. In the autumn of 1918, the Armenians' attacks on the territorial integrity of Azerbaijan increased.

The first congress of the Armenians of Nagorny-Garabakh in Shusha declared the "independence" of the region. This marked the beginning of the first major attempt to annex Nagorny-Garabakh to Armenia and the current protracted conflict.

During this period, the dual position of Western countries in the Armenian-Azerbaijani conflict affected the relations between the two countries mostly. The diplomacy of the Azerbaijan Democratic Republic made a serious effort to neutralize the British policy on the territorial integrity of Azerbaijan. This contradictory position was evident in the views of British officials on Armenians. Thus, the British diplomat Cerzon said that "after the outbreak of World War II, the main goal of His Majesty's government is the liberation of Armenians." On the other hand, at a meeting of the British government on December 9, 1918, he said, "Armenia must be handed over to France, because no one else wants to do anything with these extraordinarily unattractive people."

The two-headed British policy was manifested in the inconsistency in the issue of territorial affiliation of the Garabakh, Nakhchivan and Zangazur regions of Azerbaijan, and sometimes in support of the groundless claims of the Armenians.

There are a number of insidious plans at the heart of Britain's dual policy. For example, the British first established their general governorates in the Nakhchivan region and then ensured that the district failed to pass to "Armenian rule."

Such intentions were also reflected in the Garabakh and Zangazur regions. One of the important issues was to overcome the threat posed to the inviolability of the lands of South-West Azerbaijan by the dual policy of Britain, which is the main state in the Caucasus. The ADR government faced strong diplomatic protests from Armenia over the organization of the Nakhchivan and Garabakh general governorates. A diplomatic war broke out between Armenia and Azerbaijan.

Also, the preservation of the territorial integrity of the ADR necessitated the obstruction of the Armenian government and Andranik's relations with General Denikin. Because during Denikin's attack on Moscow, a secret agreement was signed between him and Armenia, which greatly worried the Republican government in this matter. The Foreign Ministry of the Azerbaijan Democratic Republic has taken a number of measures to prevent Armenian claims and confrontations in the Nakhchivan region of the embassy in İrevan. After the withdrawal of British troops from the region, there was an increase in protests in the region on the grounds of non-recognition of the Armenian government. For this reason, Armenia had to strengthen its borders by gathering Turkish troops in Nakhchivan. The resistance of the Turkish-Muslim population in the Nakhchivan region intensified. Already in July 1919, the Armenian administration in the region collapsed[10].

During this period, America's conflicting position was reaffirmed in the speeches of the American colonel W. Haskel, who was sent to the region. In August 1919, in a speech to parliament in İrevan, the Allied High Commissioner to Armenia, American Colonel W. Haskel, supported the Armenian territorial claims to Nakhchivan and accused Azerbaijan of violating the British-defined borders. On the one hand, Haskel stressed that his main task in the South Caucasus was to prevent armed clashes between Armenia and Azerbaijan and to create a "modus vivende". On the other hand, he stated that he recognized Zangazur and Garabakh as part of the ADR[11].

Ali Sabri Gasimov, a diplomat who fought for the preservation of Nakhchivan's autonomy during the republican period, wrote in a memorandum to the Transcaucasian High Commissioner Haskel: "Nakhchivan will defend its independence until its last breath. We do not recognize the government called Armenia. We reject the government with all our might because we want the determination of destiny. This is our right, we do not give it to anyone. If these demands are not accepted, Nakhchivanis will defend their independence with weapons." And Transcaucasian High Commissioner Haskel answered: "Tell Mr. Sabri that I am a soldier. I have nothing to do with politics ...". This fact confirmed how unsuccessful the West's policy was in Azerbaijan[12].

The failure of the Azerbaijani-Armenian conference in December 1919 and the expansion of military operations by the Dashnak armed forces dashed hopes of ensuring stability between the two countries. Armenians not only failed to ensure peace in the region by playing a diplomatic game. On the contrary, political and military conflicts between the two countries have intensified.

From the first days of November 1919, the Armenians resumed military operations in Zangazur. As the situation worsened, Azerbaijan withdrew its troops from Zangazur in accordance with the November 23 agreement, while Armenia not only withdrew its regular troops from the region, but continued its military operations by bringing in additional forces, killing some civilians and expelling others. As for the positions of the Western missions in the Caucasus on these issues, they were still largely satisfied with diplomatic warnings. Most importantly, they tried to do the impossible again, that is, to settle the problem in a way and at a level that would satisfy both sides at the same time.

The reasons for the postponement of the Azerbaijani-Armenian conference, scheduled to open on November 26, 1919 in Baku, are also interesting.

The Armenian side delayed the conference due to the fact that the planned part of the task of seizing new territories and ethnic cleansing through military operations has not yet been completed. Finally, the Azerbaijan-Armenia conference was held on December 14, 1919 in Baku. The Azerbaijani side assessed the settlement of territorial disputes as the main task of the conference. Therefore, they offered to start discussing territorial issues firstly. Armenian diplomats Arutunyan and Bekzadyan said that the necessary conditions and time have not yet been reached for a definitive solution of territorial issues. They insisted on investigating the demarcation of refugees and temporary demarcation. In general, the conferences on the Armenian-Azerbaijani conflict held during 1918-1920 did not bring any clarity to the relations between the two countries and could not work effectively in resolving territorial border disputes.

However, the diplomacy of the ADR was able to achieve historic success. Thus, the current government of the ADR in Garabakh was recognized. The Garabakh uprising of Russian-Armenian armed forces was suppressed. Armenian armed forces were suppressed in the territory of Zangazur and the control of the Azerbaijani government over the events and processes in the region was restored.

Moreover, in March 1920, the next attack of the Armenian army on Nakhchivan was resolutely repulsed and the influence of the Armenians in the region was reduced.

Caucasus policy of the Soviet leadership in the territorial claims of Armenia against Azerbaijan

The significant increase in the Armenian population in the strategically important Garabakh region of Azerbaijan took place in the early 19th century, especially after the 1828 Turkmenchay peace treaty between Russia and Iran on the division of Azerbaijani lands.

A new stage of Tsarist Russia's colonial policy in the South Caucasus, including Azerbaijan, began in the late 1820s. By increasing the number of Christians in the Garabakh region of Azerbaijan, Russian tsarism created a real basis for strengthening its influence in the region and the implementation of colonial policy.

N.N. Shavrov openly spoke about Russia's occupation of the Caucasus and for the first time wrote about the resettlement of other nations in the area: "We started our colonial activity by relocating other peoples to the Caucasus, not the Russian population. From these colonists, who are considered undesirable elements in the homeland, we created colonies in Tiflis and Yelizavetpol provinces. They were given the best lands and various privileges".

During the Russo-Iranian wars of 1804-1813 and 1826-1828, as well as throughout the 19th century, as a result of the mass resettlement of Armenians from Iran, Turkey and South Azerbaijan to Northern Azerbaijan, including Garabakh, their number began to increase year by year. In general, during 1828-1830, 124,000 Armenians were officially resettled in the mountainous part of Garabakh, and much more unofficially - 200,000 Armenians.

The resettlement of Armenians to the South Caucasus continued in the late 19th and early 20th centuries. Only in the 13 years from 1896 to 1908, 400,000 Armenians were relocated to the South Caucasus[13].

N.N. Shavrov writes about it: "In 1896, Adjutant General Sheremetyev reported on the Armenians living in the Caucasus that their number was 900,000.

In 1908, their number reached 1.3 million, so during this period the number of Armenians increased by more than 400,000. Of the 1.3 million Armenians currently living in the Caucasus, 1 million are not indigenous. We moved them here. " As a result, the resettlement of Armenians in the territories of Azerbaijan had a serious impact on the demographic situation in the mountainous part of Garabakh, the events in the region and led to the emergence of their future territorial claims.

Taking advantage of the dream of creating a "Greater Armenia", Armenian nationalists and invaders openly carried out large-scale bloody actions against Azerbaijanis in 1905-1906. They committed massacres against peaceful Azerbaijanis in Baku, Shusha, İrevan, Nakhchivan, Ganja, Zangazur, Gazakh and Tbilisi. Armenians skillfully used the First World War, as well as the February 1917 bourgeois and October Bolshevik revolutions in Russia, and succeeded in realizing their claims under the Bolshevik banner. On March 30, 31, and April 1, 1918, Armenians disguised as Bolsheviks committed genocide in Baku with the military assistance of Soviet Russia, killing 15,000 Azerbaijanis. In April-May of the same year, Armenians committed massacres in Shamakhi, Guba, Agsu, Kurdamir, Salyan, Lankaran, killing more than 50,000 civilians by the most brutal methods.

However, the establishment of Soviet power in the South Caucasus did not remove the Garabakh issue from the agenda. Because in the depths of Soviet Russian diplomacy, the tendency to turn to tsarist foreign policy was clearly felt.

In the first years of Sovietization, this tendency of Soviet Russia's position towards Azerbaijan was more pronounced on the Nagorny-Garabakh issue. As a result, in 1923, the Armenians living in the mountainous part of the Garabakh region of Azerbaijan were given the status of an autonomous region. It is known that this policy was implemented under the auspices and direct participation of Soviet Russia. The establishment of the Nagorny-Garabakh Republic within Azerbaijan was undoubtedly the result of the far-sighted and purposeful policy of Soviet Russia, which took advantage of Armenia's territorial claims and hostility towards Azerbaijan. Subsequent history has shown that this was the basis and means for the future territorial claims of the Armenians against Azerbaijan.

In the late 1920s, Armenian nationalists, who declared Zangazur and a number of other lands to be part of the Armenian SSR, resorted to new means to further expand the policy of deporting Azerbaijanis from Armenian territory[14].

Thus, on December 23, 1947, they achieved a special decision of the USSR Council of Ministers "On the resettlement of collective farmers and other Azerbaijanis from the Armenian SSR to the Kur-Araz lowland of the Azerbaijani SSR." According to this decision, in 1948-1953, about 150,000 Azerbaijanis were deported from their historical lands at the state level and relocated to Azerbaijan.

Although the Nagorny-Garabakh issue was raised several times during the Soviet era, the Armenians and their patrons failed to achieve their goals. So they had to wait for a certain historical moment. As you know, in the second half of the 1980s, a number of changes took place in the Soviet Union under the guise of perestroika.

In this situation, the Armenians, with the help of their patrons near and far abroad, using openness and democracy to implement the idea of a "Greater Armenia", again made territorial claims to the Nagorny-Garabakh region of Azerbaijan. When the events of 1988 began, Armenian politicians and their supporters in Moscow, initially trying to aggravate the situation and attract public opinion, staged mass rallies and strikes under a long-planned plan to annex Nagorny-Garabakh to Armenia under the guise of the region's economic backwardness. If we look at the figures reflecting the situation in the autonomous region before the beginning of 1988, it is clear that in a number of areas of socio-economic development, Nagorny-Garabakh is higher than other regions of Azerbaijan and Armenia. However, subsequent events have shown that the allegations about the socio-economic backwardness of Nagorny-Garabakh are only an excuse, and the main purpose is Armenia's territorial claims against Azerbaijan.

The Soviet leadership's failure to assess the issue in a timely and principled manner and to prevent Armenia's unfounded territorial claims led to tragic clashes, first in Askeran and then in Sumgayit on January 12, 1989, based on a special plan prepared by Armenians.

The Presidium of the Supreme Soviet of the USSR, in accordance with Article 119, paragraph 14 of the USSR Constitution, maintained the status of Nagorny-Garabakh as an Autonomous Region within the Azerbaijan SSR adopted a decree on the introduction of a special form of government. By this decree, a Special Management Committee was established in the Nagorny-Garabakh Republic, which was directly subordinated to the supreme state power and administration of the USSR. Although this committee was established to prevent the escalation of international relations and to stabilize the situation in the region, on the contrary, the situation in Nagorny-Garabakh worsened during the operation of the Special Management Committee. Chairman of the Committee A.I. Volsky pursued a policy of aggravation, not stabilization. As a result of his active "efforts", in a short period of time, almost all the departments and enterprises of the region were removed from the subordination of Azerbaijan and transferred to the subordination of the center.

In all documents, Nagorny-Garabakh was excluded from Azerbaijan. This created conditions for the local Azerbaijani population to be oppressed by the Armenians and soon to be expelled en masse. The indifference of the Soviet leadership to the events, the failure to assess the demand for the annexation of Nagorny-Garabakh to Armenia in a timely manner as an attack on the territorial integrity and sovereignty of Azerbaijan, aggravated the situation.

CONCLUSION.

It is necessary to recall the well-known fact that the collapse of the Soviet empire was accompanied by bloody events in its outskirts, and this was manifested in the Nagorny-Garabakh conflict. Therefore, the study of the genesis of the Nagorny-Garabakh problem, the socio-political reasons for its geopolitical roots is of great theoretical and methodological importance.

The geopolitical aspect of the problem under study is closely related to Russia's historical and geopolitical position in the formation of the roots of the conflict and the realization of Russia's national interests in the South Caucasus as a whole. The political research of both Russian and Caucasian authors shows that the Caucasus was at the center of the geopolitical intentions of Russian tsarism in terms of both political and economic interests. The rich region, which connects Europe with Asia and the Caspian Sea with the Black Sea, has also attracted the attention of countries and peoples involved in Russia's foreign policy.

It is worth noting such a methodological principle that "modern conflicts between ethnic groups and states are the legacy of great historical events." From this point of view, the genesis of the Garabakh conflict can be taken as a clear example. History proves that the Armenians have always chosen such a tried and tested tactic to achieve their strategic goals. Besides, they tried to solve specific tasks through the timely and flexible replacement of military-political stages and measures.

The main content of this tactic is the launch of military operations after certain diplomatic and ideological acts, the cessation of hostilities and the process of resumption of the war, thus advancing towards the goal.

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